

Polarized intensity (mJy beam^{-1})

0.6

0.8

1.0

56°26'00"

03

$z_{\text{Sp}}=0.30$

25'30"

00"

24'30"

100 kpc

15^h58^m54^s51^s

48^s

45^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

